

Energy Conservation and Efficiency Practices of Valencia National High School, Mindanao, Philippines

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Abstract

This study examines the energy conservation and efficiency practices of employees at Valencia National High School (VNHS) in Bukidnon, Philippines, with the aim of proposing institutional policies that strengthen sustainability. Using a quantitative descriptive design, data were gathered from 236 employees and analyzed through descriptive statistics and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The findings indicate that while employees practice basic conservation measures, gaps remain in adopting more advanced strategies such as energy-efficient lighting and minimizing standby power. Results indicated that employees generally have positive habits ($M = 3.07$, 76.75%) in conserving energy. Respondents demonstrated strong knowledge of conservation ($M = 3.23$, 80.75%) and positive attitudes toward efficiency ($M = 3.21$, 80.25%), though results varied slightly across age groups and occupational roles. Administrators and older employees scored higher than their counterparts, while gender differences were minimal. The results suggest that individual awareness is present, but consistent behavior requires structured institutional reinforcement. Policy recommendations include scheduled use of appliances, restrictions on non-essential devices, and investment in energy-efficient technologies. The study contributes to ongoing conversations on school-based sustainability and highlights the importance of aligning employee behavior with institutional policy.

Key Words: Energy conservation, efficiency practices, sustainability, educational policy, public schools

1. Introduction

The increasing demand for electricity worldwide has raised urgent concerns about sustainability, efficiency, and cost. Schools play a vital role in this discussion. They are not only significant energy consumers but also serve as learning environments where sustainable practices can be modeled and internalized by future generations (Al-Ghamdi & Kouziokas, 2014). In the Philippines, rising electricity costs and dependence on non-renewable energy have made conservation a pressing issue for educational institutions. Aligning with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7 on affordable and clean energy, schools must adopt more deliberate strategies to reduce consumption and foster a culture of responsibility (DOE, 2011; Official Gazette, 2004).

Basic conservation measures, such as switching off unused appliances and maximizing natural lighting, are common and accessible (Brännlund et al., 2007). Yet evidence shows that awareness of such practices does not always guarantee their consistent application. Long-term behavioral change often requires structured reinforcement through leadership, policy, and institutional support (Abrahamse et al., 2005; Delmas & Lessem, 2014).

In the Philippine context, several studies affirm this. Tan (2019) noted that many school employees are aware of conservation measures, but their application remains inconsistent without policy frameworks. Tan (2022) likewise emphasized that institutional mechanisms are necessary to turn awareness into sustained action. Complementing these, Tan and Tan (2020) highlighted that leadership-driven initiatives, when aligned with shared community values, are particularly effective in embedding conservation practices. However, only a few research investigations were transformed into policy and guidelines to strengthen energy conservation practices.

Building on these insights, the present study investigates the conservation habits, knowledge, and attitudes of employees at VNHS. It further analyzes how demographic factors such as age, gender, and occupation influence these practices and identifies areas where institutional policies can strengthen sustainability. By bridging the gap between individual awareness and institutional reinforcement, this study aims to provide practical recommendations for schools seeking to integrate conservation into daily operations and long-term planning that eventually become part of its policy guidelines.

2. Methodology

This research employed a quantitative descriptive design to have baseline information as data-driven foundation for policy recommendations. This was also suited for systematically describing behaviors, knowledge, and attitudes in measurable terms. The approach allowed the researchers to evaluate existing practices at VNHS and identify areas for improvement that could scientifically inform policy makers to come up with research-driven guidelines.

Respondents

A total of 236 employees participated, including administrators, teaching faculty, and non-teaching staff. The diversity of the sample ensured representation across age, gender, and academic disciplines. Respondents participated voluntarily and provided informed consent before completing the survey.

Instrument

A structured questionnaire was developed, guided by the Philippine Electrical Code (DOE, 2011) and adapted from prior studies on energy use in educational institutions (Al-Ghamdi & Kouziokas, 2014; Paço & Lavrador, 2017). The instrument had three main sections: energy consumption habits, energy conservation knowledge, and attitudes and behaviors. Responses were measured on a four-point Likert scale (1 = Poor to 4 = Very Good).

Pilot Testing

The questionnaire underwent a pilot test among a small group of employees who were not part of the final sample. Feedback led to revisions that improved clarity and ensured contextual relevance.

3. Data Collection and Analysis

The finalized instrument was distributed in both print and digital forms. Respondents were given ample time, and confidentiality was assured. Ethical standards were followed throughout. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, percentage, standard deviation) to summarize results. ANOVA and independent t-tests examined demographic differences, while correlation analysis explored the relationships among knowledge, habits, and attitudes. Analyses were conducted using Jamovi (version 2.3) and R software (version 4.1).

4. Results and Discussion

Employees reported generally positive habits ($M = 3.07$, 76.75%), with many turning off lights and appliances when not in use. While these simple actions contribute to reduced consumption, adoption of more advanced measures—such as energy-efficient lighting and minimizing standby power—was limited. This echoes findings by Brännlund et al. (2007), who observed that individuals often practice low-cost, low-effort conservation but hesitate to adopt measures requiring investment. Abrahamse et al. (2005) similarly found that behaviors with delayed or less visible

benefits are less likely to be adopted. Comparable patterns have been observed in Philippine schools (Cuyegkeng & Favis, 2019).

Knowledge levels were relatively high ($M = 3.23$, 80.75%). Most respondents reported awareness of energy-saving strategies and recognized their importance. This supports evidence that knowledge is a strong predictor of conservation behavior (Paço & Lavrador, 2017; Al-Ghamdi & Kouziokas, 2014). In the local context, Tan (2024) argued that schools with clear institutional policies can reinforce awareness, leading to greater consistency in practice.

Employees also demonstrated positive attitudes ($M = 3.21$, 80.25%), with many expressing willingness to adopt efficient technologies and a sense of responsibility toward conservation. This aligns with studies emphasizing the influence of organizational culture on employee willingness to conserve (Delmas & Lessem, 2014; Houde & Aldy, 2017). Tan (2024) further observed that leadership-driven programs enhance collective commitment in schools, ensuring that favorable attitudes translate into concrete behaviors.

Analysis revealed that age was positively associated with conservation, with older employees showing stronger knowledge and behaviors (Schipper & Bartlett, 2006). Occupational role also mattered: administrators reported the highest levels of conservation, echoing Eames and Dixon (2006). Gender differences were minimal, consistent with Paço and Lavrador (2017). Cuyegkeng and Favis (2019) likewise reported that when institutional conditions are similar, gender rarely predicts conservation practices.

Disciplinary backgrounds influenced results. Employees in TLE, ESP, and Filipino reported the most positive results, while MAPEH scored lowest. This suggests that applied and values-based disciplines are more conducive to sustainability, a pattern highlighted by Glover and Payne (2018) and Sterling (2001).

Correlation analysis showed that higher knowledge levels were linked to better habits ($r = 0.350$) and stronger attitudes ($r = 0.434$). This supports findings that knowledge serves as a foundation for behavior change (Abrahamse et al., 2005; Delmas & Lessem, 2014). Locally, Tan (2024) observed that employees with greater awareness consistently practiced conservation. ANOVA results revealed no significant differences across demographic groups (Lean & Smyth, 2010).

Taken together, the findings indicate that VNHS employees are aware of and willing to conserve energy, yet institutional reinforcement is necessary to ensure consistency. Similar to Tancredi et al. (2020), who found that awareness programs reduce consumption only when supported by policy, this study suggests that institutional frameworks are critical. Cuyegkeng and Favis (2019) recommended embedding conservation into operational policies, and highlighted that policy-driven approaches foster accountability and long-term commitment.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that VNHS employees display generally positive energy conservation habits, knowledge, and attitudes, though improvements are needed in areas requiring technological investment and institutional reinforcement. Differences across age and occupational groups suggest that leadership and experience contribute to stronger practices, while gender has minimal influence.

To strengthen conservation, the school should adopt a comprehensive institutional policy that specifies rules for appliance use, air-conditioning schedules, and restrictions on non-essential devices. Investments in efficient technologies such as LED lighting and upgraded appliances should be prioritized to reduce long-term consumption. Regular training and awareness programs are also essential to maintain motivation and deepen employees' understanding. Establishing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms will ensure compliance and track progress. Finally, sustainability values should be integrated across disciplines so that conservation is reinforced not only in operations but also in teaching and learning.

By adopting these measures, VNHS can move from awareness to consistent practice, aligning itself with national energy goals and contributing to global sustainability initiatives.

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